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EVIDENCE: THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO ILLEGAL EVIDENCE

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Abstract

The article examines the importance of evidence and its characteristics in criminal proceedings. The author analyzes a number of theoretical approaches to illegal evidence in the context of the characteristics of evidence and summarizes their features. At the same time, the opinions of a number of authors were also addressed and the shortcomings of theoretical approaches were highlighted. This approach was used in the article.

Keywords: *Criminal Procedure Code; Evidence; Illegal evidence; Theory; Substantiation.*

The third section of the new CPC is also entirely devoted to evidence and proof. The concept of evidence, its types, its acquisition, verification, evaluation, possibility, etc., in short, the reflection of procedural norms related to evidence in the new CPC indicates that the CPC occupies an important place in the country's legislative system.

Evidence, by its nature, has a certain form and content as information reflecting certain circumstances. The form of evidence reflects the means of availability of information about individual circumstances of the case in the form of information about this or that person, changes in objects, traces on objects, etc. The form of evidence is the legally prescribed sources of information about the facts relevant to the case [3; p.9].

Evidence that helps to re-describe an event that happened in the past has a number of characteristics:

1) Evidence must be real. What can be evidence must be part of the truth and must be able to be studied with any of our 5 senses. Evidence such as statements and documents have this characteristic.

2) Evidence must be logical. Only things that can reasonably express the truth can be evidence. Therefore, it is mandatory that what can be evidence be rational and scientifically acceptable.

3) Only evidence related to the issues that need to be proven is important in terms of proving. There is no need to examine evidence that is not useful.

4) Evidence must be of a character that can represent the event. The aim here is that the means used as evidence must be a part of the event and (or) reflect the event. What does not represent a part of the event is of no evidentiary value. The first condition for being able to represent is that the evidence is reliable. This is determined by the judge. Evidence that, although it represents the event, is not in accordance with reason, science, truth and law cannot be considered a means of proof.

5) Evidence must be legal. This is the most important feature required of a piece of evidence. In fact, in order for evidence with the above-mentioned features to be significant in terms of criminal proceedings, it is mandatory to obtain it legally. Therefore, it is necessary that the means of proof used in proving an event be legally acceptable. In other words, the "principle of

freedom of evidence" in criminal procedural law is not unlimited (Article 125 of the CPM) [4; p.215].

One of the authors, K. Huseynova, notes that the criminal procedural legislation of our republic does not provide a specific definition of evidence obtained by violating the law. In this regard, the author believes that it would be appropriate to establish the following definition in the legislation: "Evidence obtained by violating the rights and freedoms of man and citizen guaranteed by the Constitution, or the rules for obtaining it established by criminal procedural legislation, as well as from sources not established by law, as well as by a person who does not have the authority to do so, or as a result of actions not provided for in procedural norms, should be considered evidence obtained by violating the law" [3; pp. 21-22]. It is possible to agree with the author's opinion, since we observe that the features characterizing the essence of illegal evidence are given in the mentioned definition.

Undoubtedly, one of the most important constitutional and legal foundations of criminal proceedings is the requirements stipulated in Parts III and IV of Article 63 of the Constitution [1]. In general, when we look at the regulations contained in international law and national law, we can see that many restrictions have been placed on the investigation of material truth in criminal proceedings. Therefore, it has become clear that the purpose of modern criminal proceedings is not to investigate material truth at any cost. Therefore, a number of restrictions have been introduced into criminal proceedings in terms of investigating material truth. The most important of these is that illegal evidence is not allowed to be used during the trial.

The purpose of criminal proceedings has undergone certain changes throughout history. In the early days, the goal was to punish a person whose guilt was previously accepted. Therefore, criminal proceedings were also adapted to this goal. During this period, the concept of evidence obtained by illegal means did not exist. Therefore, evidence was evaluated and used as evidence regardless of the form in which it was obtained. In modern times, the goal of criminal proceedings is the investigation of material truth. However, the acceptance that material truth will not be investigated by any means is a prohibition on the evaluation of illegal evidence as evidence.

The Turkish Constitutional Court states in a decision that illegality primarily means a violation of all legal rules in force within our national legislative system. In this context, all actions that contradict the Constitution, international treaties, laws and other legal acts adopted in accordance with the law are included in the concept of illegality [6].

The oldest approach to the evaluation of unlawful evidence is the absolute admission approach. The logical idea on which the advocates of this approach base their arguments is as follows: "Since the main purpose of criminal proceedings is to reveal the material truth, everything that is conducive to revealing the material truth can be evaluated as evidence". Therefore, all evidence that serves to reveal the material truth should be taken into account in the formation of the judge's internal conviction. The second main argument in connection with this approach is that the purpose of criminal proceedings is limited to investigating the alleged crime. According to this argument, the judge is not a person who holds a meeting on a city bus and judges everyone who gets on the bus without paying the fare. Nor is the judge in a position to investigate all the crimes he accidentally encounters during the criminal trial and punish the perpetrators. If there is an illegality in obtaining evidence, this situation should not prevent the use of evidence to resolve the dispute, but such illegality can be disputed before another court. The reason for this is that the court hearing the case cannot ignore the evidence about the real dispute. The objection has been made against this argument that it ignores the moral aspect of criminal justice and that resorting to unfair methods by a justice body, even for the purpose of detecting a crime, will cast a shadow on the legitimacy of the trial. Another important argument is related to the existence of a public interest in solving crimes [5; p.150].

However, in our opinion, we cannot agree with this approach. Because this approach has the character of weakening the rule of law and creates a counter-effect that encourages state bodies to irresponsible behavior, not considering themselves limited by law.

The absolute exclusion approach unequivocally rejects the assessment of illegal evidence as evidence. This approach considers it harmful to accept exceptions based on various criteria in terms of the assessment of evidence, and thus to evaluate some of the illegal evidence as evidence. Many grounds have been put forward to support the absolute exclusion approach. The first of these is the reliability argument. According to the expression "reliability", a confession obtained under suspicious circumstances in criminal proceedings cannot be trusted, the information provided by this confession may lead to false internal thinking. If evidence is obtained as a result of a violation of fundamental rights and freedoms, subjecting this evidence to the prohibition of assessment will ensure the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms. The logical conclu-

sion of this argument is that evidence obtained by violating the fundamental rights of the accused cannot be used against the accused. In other words, if the evidence obtained by violating the rights of the accused is in his favor, there is no problem here. Otherwise, depriving the accused, whose rights have been violated and whose situation has been aggravated, of evidence in his favor will make him worse off. This result is unacceptable. For this reason, although the theory of protection is one of the theories that forms the basis of the absolute rejection approach, it is directed towards a relative (variable) approach. Another argument of those who defend the absolute rejection approach is to remove or encourage the authorities to be disciplined. Therefore, the reason for excluding illegal evidence from evaluation is to remove the authorities from resorting to illegal means.

Another approach, the relativity approach, emphasizes the need to resolve the issue in the assessment of illegal evidence according to the characteristics of a specific case. Therefore, some illegal evidence may be taken into account in the final decision, while others may not. The authority to determine this will belong to the court. This approach will prevent unfair situations that the radicalism of approaches that provide for absolute acceptance and absolute rejection in the assessment of illegal evidence may lead to, and will also meet the need for individualization of justice. The most serious criticism of this approach is that, since there is no certainty in which cases illegal evidence will be taken into account and in which cases it will not be taken into account, it will lead to arbitrariness and subjective assessments. Here, the idea that "giving the judge the right to choose in a controversial issue is the same as arbitrariness" that exists in continental European legal thought also plays a significant role [5; p.155].

When analyzing the relevant norm of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, we see that our legislation expresses a position of absolute rejection of illegal evidence. However, it is clear from the text of Article 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code that in some cases, evidence obtained by illegal means may be considered as evidence.

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